

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN WRITING SELF-EFFICACY AND STUDENTS' ACADEMIC SATISFACTION AT UNIVERSITY LEVEL

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ABSTRACT

Present study aimed to examine relationship between students' writing self-efficacy and academic satisfaction at university level. The study was correlational in nature. Sample of the study was comprised of 200 university students. The research instrument Writing Self-Efficacy Index (RWSI) scale developed by Ho (2016) was adopted to conduct the study. Reliability of the instrument was .842. The second instrument Academic Satisfaction scale was adopted by the researcher and reliability value of the scale was .779. Data were analysed by using inferential statistics. Study findings revealed that a significant strong correlation between writing self-efficacy and students' academic satisfaction was found at university level. Findings further revealed significant mean difference existed between male and female students' writing self-efficacy, however an insignificant difference was found between male and female students' academic satisfaction at university level. On the other hand, an insignificant mean difference existed among university students' writing self-efficacy based on their degree program and age was found, whereas a significant mean difference existed among university students' academic satisfaction based on their degree program and age.

Keywords: Academic satisfaction, Writing self-efficacy, University students

INTRODUCTION

Self-efficacy in writing refers to an individual's belief in their own ability and confidence to effectively write in a specific situation. These personal beliefs influence how individuals feel, think, motivate themselves, and take action when it comes to writing (Huerta et al., 2017). Self-efficacy relates to an individual's belief in their ability to perform a specific task or achieve a particular level of proficiency. These convictions play a pivotal role in shaping an individual's

cognitive processes, emotional responses, self-motivation, and behavioral patterns. The definition of writing attitudes has displayed inconsistency among researchers, despite attitudes being a focal point in psychological research. Ekholm et al. (2018) propose that attitudes can be viewed as either a general disposition or specific to a particular domain. Moreover, attitudes can be regarded as either temporary states or enduring traits (Camping et al., 2020). Individuals may hold

either positive or negative attitudes toward a specific writing task (state), or they may possess positive or negative attitudes toward writing tasks in general.

Writing apprehension also referred to as composition anxiety or writing block, characterizes a condition in which individuals encounter anxiety or resistance when engaged in writing. This condition is not universally present in every aspect of an individual's writing endeavors, and its intensity can vary depending on the specific writing situation. For instance, someone may not feel apprehensive when writing a report on sociology but may grapple with multiple revisions when composing a paper on a novel. Literature supports the notion that writing apprehension is influenced by the context in which writing occurs. Students, for instance, may experience heightened apprehension when tasked with writing a dissertation compared to composing an essay (Huwari & Abd Aziz, 2011). It's crucial to emphasize that writing apprehension is not an inherent trait but rather develops through negative experiences with writing (Hassan, 2001). People are not inherently predisposed to be apprehensive about writing; rather, situational demands and negative experiences contribute to shaping their anxiety. Additionally, unrealistic expectations concerning one's writing abilities can contribute to increased anxiety.

Observations reveal that students characterized by elevated anxiety levels often refrain from enrolling in writing courses and may exhibit irregular attendance patterns (Cheng, 2002). Furthermore, Onwuegbuzie and Collins (2001) highlighted through their research that graduate students experiencing heightened apprehension are prone to generating papers and proposals that are less developed compared to their counterparts with lower levels of apprehension. Expanding on this clarify that heightened levels of writing apprehension can result in various issues for students, including class avoidance, late or non-submission of papers, and a preference for sitting at the back of the class.

Moreover, existing literature indicates that writing apprehension is a prevalent phenomenon not only among non-native English writers but also among writers in general (Altukruni, 2019). Additionally,

it is valuable to investigate the correlation between writing apprehension and demographic factors like age, gender, academic level, and socioeconomic status, as these variables can potentially impact the extent of writing apprehension experienced by students. Studies have demonstrated that heightened levels of writing apprehension are more frequently observed in native writers, especially among undergraduate students (McAllister, 2014), as well as postgraduate students in research conducted by (Huwari & Abd Aziz, 2011). It is crucial to recognize that learners exhibit varying degrees of writing apprehension, with some encountering high levels while others experience lower levels. Several factors contribute to elevated levels of writing apprehension, including the fear of receiving negative feedback, comments, and evaluation from teachers. Additionally, a lack of self-confidence is identified as a significant factor (Rezaei & Jafari, 2014). Limited linguistic knowledge or an insufficient understanding of English structure also plays a role along with inadequate knowledge about academic writing. Negative attitudes toward writing, past negative writing experiences (Al-Shboul & Huwari, 2015), time constraints, the nature of the writing task or subject (Lin & Ho, 2009), and learners' negative perceptions of themselves are additional contributing factors.

Academic Satisfaction

The education system is essential to the growth of every country. Brunat (2006) established the link between economic growth and education. Globally, a country's economic growth is most strongly represented by its human capital. Every nation's growth and prosperity are positively impacted when its human capital is developed through education (Coleman, 2005). Service customers have high expectations for educational service providers due to the growing demand for education and awareness of viable alternatives (Petruzzellis & Romanazzi 2010). Examining the education industry is an intriguing field of study from a research standpoint.

Not only does it affect the economy of the nation, but it also raises questions about the quality of education being given to students, their degree of

accomplishment and contentment, and their capacity for absorption. After all, these individuals are the country's future. It is true that this fiercely competitive sector is always faced with new challenges and changes as it works to manage students' rising expectations while also trying to adjust to the realities of the outside world (Sohail & Shaikh 2004).

In an effort to comprehend the psychosocial dynamics of student satisfaction, a number of hypotheses have been put forth. According to the "happy-productive" student paradigm (Cotton, Dollard, & de Jonge, 2002), for instance, psychosocial elements like coping, stress, and wellbeing may operate as a mediating factor in student happiness. They offered proof that higher psychological distress levels at university were associated with decreased satisfaction, based on the "happy-productive" idea.

Academic and educational planners, as well as university administration, are primarily concerned with the academic satisfaction levels of their pupils. As a result, it has prompted several scholars to investigate various facets of the academic experience and how students perceive it. University student satisfaction has been the subject of numerous research. Course content, social characteristics and/or possibilities, campus aesthetics, and the helpfulness and teaching qualities of the personnel are some pretty consistent contributing components (Garcia-Aracil, 2009).

Wiers-Jenssen et al. (2002) looked at how broad components of students' learning experiences might be used to analyze total student satisfaction. The results of the analysis showed that academic and pedagogical teaching quality was a significant factor in determining student happiness. The study also stressed that when evaluating factors that affect student satisfaction, it is important to take into account the social environment, attractive features of the physical infrastructure, the quality of services provided by the administrative staff, the supervision and feedback provided by the academic staff, the composition, content, and relevance of the curriculum, the quality of, and access to, leisure activities. According to this study, academic satisfaction is a multifaceted notion that can be broken down into

three categories: satisfaction with textbooks, teachers and staff, and college administration.

There are several ways to define and measure student satisfaction; these are outside the scope of this paper and are not covered here (Marzo-Navarro et al., 2005). Numerous elements were presented in the literature as drivers of students' satisfaction; some of these factors had to do with the traits and behaviours of the students, while others had to do with the educational process or the way universities operated.

In contrast, Umbach and Porter (2002) examined how certain departmental features, such as research, the percentage of female undergraduates, and faculty contact with students, affected students' satisfaction with their education; Hartman and Schmidt (1995) examined the relationship between institutional performance and program outcomes and discovered that assessments of students' satisfaction with higher education were influenced by both the perceived quality and the perceived outcomes of the service provider's performance; Grunwald and Peterson (2003) also examined institutional factors, including students' assessments of teaching activities and administrative support; Misane and Tadesse (2014) examined factors that influence staff and student satisfaction with services and revealed that. The general happiness of university students is a pertinent topic to research, primarily because of its strong correlation with subjective well-being and contentment, which makes it a potential measure of the caliber of educational services. As per this approach, various angles have been used to analyze the pleasure of university students. As per their perspective, life happiness can be subdivided into contentment with one's university experience.

Statement of the Problem

Present was aimed to examine relationship between writing self-efficacy and students' academic satisfaction at university level.

Objective of the Study

1. To examine relationship between writing self-efficacy and students' academic satisfaction at university level

Research Methodology

Present study was correlational in nature. Sample of the study was comprised of 200 university students. The research instrument comprises of 11 items, aligned with the Research Writing Self-Efficacy Index (RWSI) scale developed by Ho (2016) was adopted to conduct the study. Reliability of the instrument was .842. The second instrument academic satisfaction was adopted by the researcher and reliability value of the scale was

.779. Data were analysed by using Pearson r to find out relationship between the variables. Significant effect was calculated by using linear regression. An independent samples t-test was applied to find out the differences of male and female university students' writing self-efficacy and academic satisfaction, whereas differences among university students' writing self-efficacy and academic satisfaction based on their degree program and age was calculated by using one-way ANOVA.

Results

Table 1

Correlation between Writing Self-efficacy and Students' Academic Satisfaction at University Level

Variables	N	M	SD	r- value	Sig.
Writing Self-efficacy	200	36.73	7.72	.678**	.000
Academic Satisfaction	200	97.50	11.96		

Correlation between writing self-efficacy and academic satisfaction was conducted by using Pearson's r. A significant strong positive

correlation between students' writing self-efficacy and academic satisfaction was found at university level.

Table 2

Effect of Writing Self-efficacy on Students' Academic Satisfaction at University Level

Model	Unstandardized Co-efficient	Standardized Co-efficient	β	t	p	df	F	R ²
	β	Std. Error β						
Writing Self-Efficacy	58.942	3.039	.678	12.96	.000	199	168.10	.456
Academic Self-efficacy	1.050	.081						

A significant effect of students' writing self-efficacy on their academic satisfaction was predicted

significantly with the value of ($R^2 = .456$, $\beta = .678$, $F=168.10$, $p=.000$).

Table 3

Independent Samples t-test for Comparison between Male and Female Students' Writing Self-Efficacy and Academic Satisfaction

Variables	Gender	N	M	SD	df	t- value	Sig.
Writing Self-Efficacy	Male	100	36.32	8.62	186.97	-.750	.004
	Female	100	37.14	6.72			
Academic Satisfaction	Male	100	94.19	11.72	198	-4.062	.943
	Female	100	100.81	11.32			

Findings calculated by using independent samples t-test concluded that there was significant mean difference existed between male and female students' writing self-efficacy, however an

insignificant difference was found between male and female students' academic satisfaction at university level.

Table 4

One-way ANOVA for Comparison among University Students' Writing Self-Efficacy based on their Degree Program

Variable	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Writing Self- efficacy	168.393	2	84.197	1.418	.245
	11701.027	197	59.396		
	11869.420	199			

Findings calculated by using one-way ANOVA concluded that there was insignificant mean

difference existed among university students' writing self-efficacy based on their degree program.

Table 5

One-way ANOVA for Comparison among University Students' Academic Satisfaction based on their Degree Program

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Academic Satisfaction	3445.567	2	1722.784	13.554	.000
	25040.433	197	127.109		
	28486.000	199			

Findings calculated by using one-way ANOVA concluded that there was significant mean difference existed among university students'

academic satisfaction based on their degree program.

Table 5 (a)

Post hoc Analysis for Comparison among University Students' Academic Satisfaction within their Degree Program

(I) Program	(J) Program	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
Graduate	MPhil	-8.93857*	1.75697	.000
	PhD	-1.21000	2.34692	.864
MPhil	Graduate	8.93857*	1.75697	.000
	PhD	7.72857*	2.46024	.005
PhD	Graduate	1.21000	2.34692	.864
	MPhil	-7.72857*	2.46024	.005

Post hoc analysis was conducted to find out difference among university students' academic satisfaction within groups of their degree program. Findings of the study revealed that students having

graduate degree were significantly different from the students having qualification of MPhil and PhD.

Table 6

One-way ANOVA for Comparison among University Students' Writing Self-Efficacy based on their Age

Variable	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Writing Self- efficacy	318.613	2	159.306	2.717	.069
	11550.807	197	58.634		
	11869.420	199			

Findings calculated by using one-way ANOVA concluded that there was insignificant mean

difference existed among university students' writing self-efficacy based on their age.

Table 7

One-way ANOVA for Comparison among University Students' Academic Satisfaction based on their Age

Variable	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Academic Satisfaction	5092.427	2	2546.214	21.442	.000
	23393.573	197	118.749		
	28486.000	199			

Findings calculated by using one-way ANOVA concluded that there was significant mean

difference existed among university students' satisfaction based on their age.

Table 7 (a)

Post hoc Analysis for Comparison among University Students' Academic Satisfaction within their Age

(I) Age	(J) Age	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
21-30 Years	31-40 Years	-14.29485*	2.18768	.000
	41-50 Years	-2.83985	1.72043	.227
31-40 Years	21-30 Years	14.29485*	2.18768	.000
	41-50 Years	11.45500*	2.31751	.000
41-50 Years	21-30 Years	2.83985	1.72043	.227
	31-40 Years	-11.45500*	2.31751	.000

Post hoc analysis was conducted to find out difference among university students' academic satisfaction within their age groups. Findings of the study revealed that students having age group of 21-30 years were significantly different from the students having age groups of 31-40 and 41-45 at $p \leq .05$ level of significance.

Conclusion

Present study aimed to examine relationship between students' writing self-efficacy and academic satisfaction at university level. Study findings revealed that a significant strong correlation between writing self-efficacy and students' academic satisfaction was found at university level. Findings further revealed significant mean difference existed between male and female students' writing self-efficacy, however an insignificant difference was found between male and female students' academic satisfaction at university level. On the other hand, an insignificant mean difference existed among university students' writing self-efficacy based on their degree program and age was existed, whereas a significant mean difference existed among university students' academic satisfaction based on their degree program and age.

Recommendations

Following are the recommendations of the study.

1. The research results highlighted the importance of fostering a stronger correlation between writing self-efficacy and academic satisfaction. It is obvious that students who have

high levels of writing self-efficacy leads them toward academic satisfaction at university level.

2. An in-depth investigation might be helpful to identify students' writing self-efficacy and academic satisfaction at university level.

3. It is recommended to conduct training workshops, awareness channels and different methods to train students through mentoring to develop writing skills which increase their academic satisfaction.

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